

COMUNNICATION, DISSEMINATION & EXPLOTATION PLAN

Deliverable 1.3

PROJECT

Project number: 101109977

Project acronym: TaphArt

Project name: TaphArt: exploring the potential existence of rock art paintings in the Middle Stone Age of southern Africa and its destruction due to the action of taphonomic processes

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Date: 30-07-2025

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1. Executive summary

This Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan details the measures undertaken to maximise the impact of the MSCA-funded TaphArt project. It sets out how communication efforts were designed to inform and engage the public, showcase the activities and highlight the benefits of the research. Dissemination and exploitation actions ensure that the knowledge generated reaches intended audiences and can be reused, thereby extending the project's influence beyond its duration. In this sense, the plan defines a public-engagement strategy aimed at reaching a wide audience while ensuring that scientific outputs are disseminated via peer-reviewed publications, conference presentations and open-access repositories. By documenting these measures and the rationale behind them, the plan demonstrates compliance with Horizon Europe requirements and reflects a commitment to delivering benefits for both the scientific community and the wider public.

2. The MSCA TaphArt Project

The advent of symbolic material culture and the storage of information outside the human brain through the production of artefacts and images imbued with meaning was a landmark in human evolution. Although it has been generally considered as the consequence of an European Upper Palaeolithic "revolution" that took place around 40 ka, new evidence from the Middle Stone Age (MSA, ~300–40 ka) suggests the presence of symbolic material culture in Africa at ~150 ka. In this context, a major research challenge for archaeology is to explain the apparent absence of rock art paintings in the MSA archaeological record of southern Africa. Ochre pigments are ubiquitous in the sites from this period, and toolkits used to produce ochre-rich liquid paint date from at least ~100 ka. Furthermore, images engraved on pieces of ochre and a crayon drawing demonstrate that the MSA populations had all the material, technical and cognitive resources necessary to create graphic representations.

Thus, through an innovative and interdisciplinary approach that brings together an international team of experts in archaeology, paleoenvironmental science, atmospheric science, material science, and analytical chemistry—from the University of Bordeaux, the University of the Basque Country, and the German Aerospace Center—the TaphArt project aims to develop an experimental research to systematically investigate whether the absence of rock art paintings in the MSA sites of southern Africa is due to a cultural choice of the human populations or the result of taphonomic processes that eliminated the painted images from the archaeological record.

Taking as reference the archaeological and paleoenvironmental context of Blombos Cave (South Africa) (Fig. 1), the project tests the hypothesis that marine aerosol and wind erosion may have contributed to the destruction of rock art paintings potentially produced on the site. In this sense, the data generated through accelerated ageing experiments and the application of archaeometric techniques, such as 3D digital and confocal microscopy, micro-EDXRF mapping, Raman spectroscopy, and hyperspectral imaging, are providing groundbreaking unprecedented insights into the origins of rock art and the behavioural evolution of *Homo sapiens*.

Fig. 1 – General view of Blombos Cave (South Africa).

3. Dissemination activities for the scientific community

This section summarises the dissemination actions undertaken during the project to share results with the academic and specialist community, in line with Horizon Europe’s open science and impact objectives. Activities were designed to ensure that findings were made accessible to peers, potential users, and domain experts across relevant disciplines, facilitating knowledge exchange and uptake. To that end, dissemination efforts were guided by the FAIR principles—ensuring that all data and research outputs were Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable—thus enhancing the long-term visibility and usability of the project’s results.

3.1 Scientific Publications

3.1.1 Publication in peer-reviewed journals

1. Santos da Rosa, N. (2025). From questions to inferences: methodological principles for the use of experimental archaeology in rock art research. *Archaeology, Ethnology & Anthropology of Eurasia*, 53(3). Open Access. SJR Quartile 1. Accepted for publication – scheduled for release in September 2025.

This article presents the theoretical and methodological framework developed to test the central hypothesis of the TaphArt project, outlining the principles that guide the use of experimental archaeology to investigate the potential production and taphonomic loss of Middle Stone Age rock art in southern Africa

2. Medina-Alcaide, M. Á., Ramírez, A. F., López, A., Intxaurbe, I., Sanchidrián, J. L., Ferrier, C., Rodríguez-Castro, E., Romero, A. J., Pons-Branchu, E., Mesa, M. D., Úbeda-Portugués, J. M., Sánchez-Barba, L. P., Arriolabengoa, M., Santos da Rosa, N., Salceda, A., Torres, A. J., & Quiles, A. (2025). Nuevos datos para el conocimiento de la actividad prehistórica subterránea de la cueva con arte paleolítico potencial de Los Márquez (Jerez de la Frontera, Cádiz). *SPAL: Revista de Prehistoria y Arqueología*. Open Access. SJR Quartile 1. Accepted for publication – scheduled for release in December 2025.

This article presents the first results from the investigation of Los Márquez Cave, including archaeological finds, graphic expressions, and radiometric data. Taphonomic methods developed within the TaphArt project were adapted to assess the preservation and visibility of Palaeolithic signs, demonstrating their applicability beyond Middle Stone Age contexts.

3.1.2 Publication in peer-reviewed journals – Under review

1. Garate, D., Intxaurbe, I., Arriolabengoa, M., Medina-Alcaide, M. A., Fernández-Navarro, V., Spaey, O., Torres, A., Santos da Rosa, N., López, A., Salazar, S., Leblanc, J. C., & Ferrier, C. (under review). New approaches to rock art research: the contribution of a laboratory cave to the study of archaeological remains and taphonomic processes. *Journal of Field Archaeology*. SJR Quartile 1. Submitted for peer review on 10 July 2025.

This article presents the use of a laboratory cave replicating Palaeolithic conditions to carry out in situ experimental research on rock art production and preservation. The methodological framework and analytical tools developed in the TaphArt project were instrumental in designing and implementing these experiments, enabling high-resolution studies of taphonomic dynamics under controlled cave environments.

3.1.3 Publication in peer-reviewed journals – In preparation

1. Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Fiore, D., Gómez Laserna, O., Romani, M., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., Wiesinger, F., van Niekerk, K., & Henshilwood, C. (in preparation). Blowing in the wind: using accelerated ageing experiments to model the impact of aeolian erosion on coastal rock art paintings. To be submitted to *Scientific Reports* (SJR Q1) in October 2025.

This article presents the first experimental results of the TaphArt project, using accelerated ageing protocols to model the effects of aeolian erosion on painted rock surfaces. The study provides quantitative insights into the degradation of ochre-based motifs under controlled wind erosion, offering a novel framework to assess the preservation potential of coastal rock art.

2. Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Fiore, D., Gómez Laserna, O., Romani, M., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., Wiesinger, F., van Niekerk, K., & Henshilwood, C. (in preparation). The breeze of decay: an experimental approach to the impact of marine aerosol degradation in coastal rock art sites. To be submitted to the *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* (SJR Q1) in November 2025.

This article explores the impact of marine aerosol on the preservation of coastal rock art through controlled laboratory experiments. Building on the TaphArt project’s experimental design, it quantifies chemical and physical alterations induced by salt-rich atmospheric agents, contributing to predictive models of pigment degradation in coastal archaeological contexts.

3.1.4 Publication in peer-reviewed journals – To be prepared

1. Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Fiore, D., Gómez Laserna, O., Romani, M., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., Wiesinger, F., van Niekerk, K., & Henshilwood, C. (to be prepared). Developing a predictive model to estimate the preservation rate of rock art

paintings against the impact of marine aerosol degradation and wind erosion: a case study from the Southern Cape coast of South Africa. Intended for submission to *Quaternary Science Reviews* (expected January 2026).

This forthcoming article will integrate experimental results with palaeoenvironmental data to develop a predictive model for estimating the preservation rates of rock art exposed to marine aerosol and wind erosion. Focusing on the southern Cape coast of South Africa, it refines our understanding of taphonomic impacts on Middle Stone Age painted imagery in coastal areas.

2. Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Fiore, D., Gómez Laserna, O., Romani, M., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., Wiesinger, F., van Niekerk, K., & Henshilwood, C. (to be prepared). The absence of rock art paintings in coastal Middle Stone Age sites of Southern Africa: is it the result of cultural choices or taphonomic processes? Intended for submission to the *Journal of Human Evolution* (expected March 2026).

This planned article will integrate archaeological, experimental, and palaeoenvironmental data to address a central question in African prehistory: whether the absence of rock art paintings in coastal Middle Stone Age sites reflects cultural choices or taphonomic loss. It aims to provide a robust framework for interpreting the evolution of symbolic behaviour in deep time.

3.1.5 Publications in books

1. Ruiz-Redondo, A., Barciela, V., Martorell, X., Alcolea, M., Angás, J., Daniel, M., Fernández-Peris, J., Garín-Artázcov, X., Intxaurbe, I., Martínez i Rubio, T., Molina Hernández, F. J., Santos da Rosa, N., Sierra, A., & Soler Díaz, J. A. (2025). *Arqueología del simbolismo paleolítico en el Mediterráneo peninsular: estado actual de las investigaciones en Cova Dones (Valencia)*. In: Festschrift in honour of Prof. César González Sainz. Universidad de Cantabria. Open Access. Accepted for publication – scheduled for release in November 2025.

This chapter presents the current state of multidisciplinary research at Cova Dones, a newly identified Palaeolithic rock art site in eastern Iberia. Taphonomic approaches developed within the TaphArt project are being applied to investigate the preservation of clay-based paintings, contributing to a better understanding of the site’s *chaîne opératoire* and post-depositional dynamics.

3.2 Scientific Communication Activities

3.2.1 Participation in international conferences

1. Oral communication: Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C. “TaphArt: an experimental approach to the impact of wind erosion and marine aerosol degradation on coastal rock art sites”. *30th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists*. Rome – Italy (28-31 August 2024) – Estimated audience: ~40 attendees.

2. Oral communication (invited speaker): Santos da Rosa, N. “On the taphonomy of rock art: using accelerated ageing experiments to model the impact of marine aerosol degradation and wind erosion on prehistoric paintings”. *8th International Congress “The Art of Prehistoric Societies”*. Salamanca – Spain (6-10 November 2024) – Estimated audience: ~300 attendees (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 – 8th International Conference “The Art of Prehistoric Societies” (Salamanca – Spain).

3. Oral communication: Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Fiore, D., Gómez Laserna, O., Romani, M., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., Wiesinger, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C. “Modelling the taphonomic effects of wind erosion and marine aerosol degradation on painted images through accelerated ageing experiments: implications for the origins of rock art and the evolution of human symbolic behaviour”. *10th World Archaeological Congress*. Darwin – Australia (22–28 June 2025) – Estimated audience: ~50 attendees (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 – 10th World Archaeological Congress (Darwin – Australia).

4. Oral communication: Spaey, O., Garate, D., Intxaurbe, I., Arriolabengoa, M., Medina-Alcaide, M. Á., Fernandez-Navarro, V., Torres, A., Santos da Rosa, N., López, A., Leblanc, J.-C., Ferrier, C. “The Isuntza Cave (Lekeitio, Spain): A Unique Natural Laboratory for

Experimental Study of Prehistoric Cave Art.” *7th International Conference on Experimental Archaeology*. Liège – Belgium (22–25 October 2025) – Estimated audience: ~100 attendees.

5. Session organisation: Fiore, D., & Santos da Rosa, N. “The materiality of art: conceptual, experimental and archaeometric approaches”. Independent session organised at the *10th World Archaeological Congress*. Darwin – Australia (22–28 June 2025) – Estimated audience: ~50 attendees (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 – Some of the participants of the session *The Materiality of Art: Conceptual, Experimental and Archaeometric Approaches* (Darwin – Australia).

3.2.2 Participation in workshops

1. Oral communication (invited discussant): Santos da Rosa, N. Invited discussant at the “Activating Symbolism” Workshop. University of Bergen – Norway (1 October 2024). – Estimated audience: ~25 attendees.

3.2.3 Participation in seminars

1. Oral communication (invited speaker): Santos da Rosa, N. “When replication is not enough: on the use of experimental archaeology in rock art research”. *RARI Seminar Series*, Rock Art Research Institute, University of the Witwatersrand – South Africa (30 July 2025). – Estimated audience: ~40 attendees.

2. Oral communication: Santos da Rosa, N. “TaphArt: exploring the potential existence of rock art paintings in the Middle Stone Age of southern Africa and its destruction due to the action of taphonomic processes”. *Symbol Group Meeting*, UMR5199, University of Bordeaux – France (24 October 2023). – Estimated audience: ~15 attendees.

3. Oral communication: Santos da Rosa, N. “TaphArt: exploring the potential existence of rock art paintings in the Middle Stone Age of southern Africa and its destruction due to the action of taphonomic processes”. *PACEA Scientific Meeting*, UMR5199, University of Bordeaux – France (5 October 2023) – Estimated audience: ~80 attendees (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 – PACEA Scientific Meeting (Bordeaux – France).

3.2.4 Participation in mentoring programmes

1. Oral communication (invited speaker): Santos da Rosa, N. “Mentoring Program for Postdoctoral Researchers in Heritage Science: MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships”, organised by the *Grupo Especializado de Química del Patrimonio* (Real Sociedad Española de Química). Online event hosted via Microsoft Teams (26 May 2025) (Fig. 6) Estimated audience: ~40 attendees.

**Mentoring Program for Postdoctoral Researchers
in Heritage Science:
MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships**

Clara Granzotto
The Art Institute of Chicago

Neemias Santos da Rosa
University of Bordeaux

Águeda Saenz
Instituto de Nanociencia y Materiales
de Aragón

May 26, 2025 3:30 pm (CET) Teams

Link for the connection

Workshop organized by

Fig. 6 – Mentoring program MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships (Online).

4. Dissemination activities for the general public

This section summarises the dissemination actions undertaken during the project to communicate its goals, activities, and results to the general public, in line with Horizon Europe’s open science and societal impact objectives. Efforts were designed to raise awareness about prehistoric art, promote public understanding of archaeological research, and foster inclusive dialogue around cultural heritage. To that end, dissemination initiatives prioritised accessibility, engagement, and transparency—ensuring that key messages reached diverse audiences through public lectures, citizen science actions, and digital media platforms. These measures aimed not only to inform, but also to empower individuals and communities to connect with and value the archaeological record.

4.1 Public lectures

1. Public lecture: Santos da Rosa, N. *“TaphArt Project: Exploring the potential existence of rock art paintings in coastal Middle Stone Age sites of southern Africa and its destruction due to the action of taphonomic processes”*. Presentations on Archaeology and Research in the Blombos Cave, organised by the Blombos Museum of Archaeology, Still Bay – South Africa (20 March 2024). – Estimated audience: ~120 attendees (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 – Public lecture for the community of Still Bay (South Africa).

4.2 Social media

1. Facebook: As part of its public engagement strategy, the TaphArt project has actively maintained a dedicated Facebook page to communicate with a wider audience (<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61552276132397>). Since its creation, the page has attracted 135 followers and reached a cumulative total of 4,326 content views. Posts include updates about the project progress and behind-the-scenes insights from fieldwork experimental activities. Over the last year, the page recorded 484 interactions, with 85.1% reactions, 9.9% comments, and 5% shares, reflecting strong community interest. Notably, 52.3% of interactions came from non-followers, underscoring the platform’s reach beyond its immediate audience.

2. X: The TaphArt project also maintains an active presence on X (formerly Twitter) via @MSCATaphArt, with 328 followers to date. While the platform serves as a tool for engaging academic networks, it has also played a key role in reaching the general public—particularly through accessible threads, visual content, and real-time updates from fieldwork and events.

This has helped raise awareness of the project's goals and findings among diverse audiences, including teachers, students, amateur archaeologists, and cultural heritage enthusiasts. Through consistent and approachable communication, the X account has fostered public interest in archaeology and the origins of rock art.

3. YouTube: The TaphArt project also maintains a dedicated YouTube channel — <https://www.youtube.com/@MSCATaphArtProject>— designed to support public dissemination through audiovisual media. Although still in its early stages, the channel has already gathered 29 subscribers and accumulated 749 views across its first three videos. These include an overview of the project and two short interviews with key researchers discussing its epistemological and archaeological significance in accessible terms. Eight additional videos are currently in post-production and will be released over the coming months. By providing content in video format, the channel aims to enhance outreach among general audiences, fostering broader interest in prehistoric art and archaeological science.

5. Planned future communications and dissemination activities

Several additional communication and dissemination actions are planned for the coming months and beyond the official end of the TaphArt project. An online workshop bringing together specialists in Middle Stone Age archaeology, rock art, and taphonomy is scheduled for December 2025, with the aim of discussing the project's results and their scientific implications. In parallel, a second public lecture is planned in Still Bay (South Africa) for mid-November 2025 to present the project's findings to the local community. Moreover, given that research activities initiated within the TaphArt framework will continue beyond the formal project timeline, communication and dissemination efforts will also remain ongoing. These include the publication of results in peer-reviewed journals, the presentation of findings at international conferences, and continued updates through the project's social media.

6. Citizen science engagement

As part of its commitment to open science and societal engagement, the TaphArt project incorporated a citizen science component through direct collaboration with members of the

local community of Still Bay (South Africa). This initiative aimed to foster public participation in scientific research, encourage local knowledge exchange, and promote inclusive access to archaeological practices. In particular, retired geologist Pieter-Jan Grabe played a key role in several phases of the project (Fig. 8). He participated in multiple fieldwork campaigns and contributed actively to the preparation of the accelerated ageing experiments, especially during the collection and processing of raw materials from the surroundings of Blombos Cave. His involvement not only enriched the scientific process through local geological expertise but also exemplified the value of community participation in cutting-edge archaeological research. Thus, this collaboration reflects the project's broader goal of returning knowledge to the community while creating meaningful opportunities for non-specialists to engage with and contribute to scientific inquiry.

Fig. 8 – Pieter-Jan Grabe collecting raw materials for experimental work together with Neemias Santos da Rosa (Principal Investigator of the TaphArt project) in the surroundings of Blombos Cave (South Africa).

7. Exploitation of results

The TaphArt project is producing a set of results with significant potential for future scientific, societal, and practical use. From a scientific perspective, the project lays the groundwork for a new and still-emerging line of research: the experimental study of rock art taphonomy. Its methodological innovations and interdisciplinary framework—which integrates archaeology, atmospheric science, analytical chemistry, material science, and paleoenvironmental studies—offer a replicable and scalable model for future investigations in both coastal and inland contexts. Moreover, the quantitative and qualitative data generated through accelerated ageing experiments constitute a robust reference for assessing the impact of taphonomic agents such as wind erosion and marine aerosol on painted rock surfaces.

These datasets will be particularly valuable for researchers working in similar environments across Africa and beyond, helping to interpret the presence or absence of rock art and refine models of preservation potential.

At the societal level, the project contributes to enhancing awareness of Africa's central role in the emergence of symbolic behaviour and promotes the valorisation of its archaeological heritage. Through its open-access strategy, public engagement initiatives, and incorporation of citizen science practices, the TaphArt project encourages knowledge co-creation and returns the benefits of scientific research to the wider public. Also, in terms of applied outcomes, the findings offer a scientific basis for designing more effective and economically viable conservation strategies for rock art in coastal areas, particularly in regions with limited financial resources. This makes the results not only academically impactful but also relevant to cultural heritage managers, policy-makers, and conservation professionals.

All data and protocols produced by the project will remain accessible for future use through open-access repositories, supporting their continued exploitation by the academic community and other stakeholders. In line with open science practices and the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), all publications and datasets will be made available via Zenodo and OSKAR Bordeaux. This includes preprints, peer-review reports, final versions of the articles, and two databases containing experimental data. These measures will not only enhance the visibility and impact of the research but will also enable its replication and improvement by others, fostering collaborative validation and refinement of the methodologies developed within the project.